

INITIAL CRUSH STRESS OF CELLULAR MATERIALS UNDER DYNAMIC LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic crushing of irregular honeycombs using cell-based finite element models is re-examined to solve the controversial issue on the initial crush stress of cellular materials. Local stress and strain calculation methods are employed to determine the initial crush stresses and the strain rates at initial crush. It is found that the initial crush stresses under different impact scenarios could be very different. The initial crush stress under high-constant-velocity compression is identical to the quasi-static one but less than the one under direct impact. A power-law relation between the initial crush stress and the strain rate is introduced to describe the strain-rate effect on the initial crush stress of irregular honeycomb when the local strain rate exceeds a critical value, below which there is no strain-rate effect of irregular honeycomb.

1 INTRODUCTION

The dynamic compressive behaviors of cellular materials have gained much research attention due to their excellent mechanical properties in energy absorption and shock mitigation. The nominal stress-strain relation is commonly used to represent the constitutive behavior of cellular materials, which contains three distinct stages, namely elastic, long plateau, and densification stages. This relation is suitable for the case of low-velocity compression of cellular materials, but it loses its physical meaning when the impact velocity is high enough, because the deformation is localized and the stresses at the two ends of a cellular specimen are not in balance [1]. Thus, the split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) technique may be not appropriate to test the rate-sensitive behavior of cellular materials. The direct/inverse impact techniques have been applied in the literature. It has been realized that the dynamic stress-strain states in the densification stage are very different from those of quasi-static compression [2-9], but there are some conflicting conclusions on the dynamic and quasi-static initial crush stresses in the literature [3-8]. Zheng et al. [3] stated that the dynamic initial crush stress is larger than the quasi-static one and pointed out the possible deformation mechanisms. But, Sun et al. [7] did not agree with this point and argued that the definition of shock front boundary in Ref. [3] is not enough strict. In fact, as done in Ref. [4-6], Sun et al. [7] determined the initial crush stress (named as the collapse stress in Ref. [7]) from the support end of cellular specimen, which is far from the shock front.

In this study, we present further evidences from the direct information of local stress, strain and strain rate to confirm the point that the dynamic initial crush stress is larger than the quasi-static one. Numerical simulations of irregular honeycombs under high-constant-velocity compression and under high-initial-velocity direct impact are carried out.

2 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATIONS

Numerical simulations of irregular honeycombs under dynamic loadings are performed with the aid of the finite element code ABAQUS/Explicit. Honeycomb specimens are constructed by using the 2D Voronoi technique, see Ref. [10] for details. Each specimen has a size of length 50 mm, width 50 mm

and thickness 1 mm and contains 500 cells with irregularity 0.3 and average size 2.5 mm. The relative density of honeycomb specimens is 0.1. Cell walls are modeled with S4R shell elements and the in-plane element size is about 0.2 mm determined through a mesh sensitivity analysis. The material of cell walls is assumed to be elastic, perfectly plastic with density 2700 kg/m^3 , Young's modulus 66 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.3 and yield stress 175 MPa. All nodes of a honeycomb specimen are constrained in the out-of-plane direction to simulate a plane strain situation. General contact with friction coefficient 0.02 is defined in simulations.

We consider two kinds of loading scenarios in this study, as illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2. In Fig. 1, the loading scenario is the constant-velocity compression: the honeycomb specimen is placed against a fixed rigid plate at one end (the support end or the distal end) and crushed along the X direction by a rigid plate with constant velocity V at the other end (the impact end or the proximal end). In Fig. 2, the loading scenario is the direct impact: the honeycomb specimen impinges on the rigid wall with an initial velocity V_0 along the X direction. Some deformation patterns of honeycomb specimens under the two loading scenarios with $V = 200 \text{ m/s}$ and $V_0 = 200 \text{ m/s}$ are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. In both loading scenarios, layer-wise crushing deformation bands propagate from the proximal end to the distal end in the specimen.

Figure 1: A finite element model and deformation patterns of irregular honeycomb under constant-velocity compression.

Figure 2: A finite element model and deformation patterns of irregular honeycomb under direct impact.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Local stress and initial crush stress

The cross-sectional engineering stress calculation method [11] is employed here to obtain the one-dimensional stress distribution in the loading direction. The local engineering stress along the loading direction is calculated from the internal force at Lagrangian cross-sectional location of the honeycomb specimen. The cross-sectional internal force is calculated by

$$F_X = F_X^n + F_X^c, \quad F_X^n = \sum_{i=1}^{N_1} F_{Xi}^n, \quad F_X^c = \sum_{i=1}^{N_2} (F_{Xi}^{cn} + F_{Xi}^{ct}) \quad (1)$$

where F_X^n is the nodal force, which is caused by the force transferred through the element nodes, and F_X^c is the contact force, which is caused by cell-wall contact during the deformation. The variables F_{Xi}^n , F_{Xi}^{cn} and F_{Xi}^{ct} refer to the X -directional components of nodal force, normal contact force and tangential contact force of node i , respectively. N_1 is the number of the nodes of the elements crossed by the examined cross-section in the reference configuration, and N_2 is the total number of nodes from the left end to the examined cross-section. In particular, in the case of constant-velocity compression, the nodes of the impact end are also included. The simplified calculation formula of the contact force is benefited from the Newton's third law, wherein the forces of a complete contact pair cancel each other. The force information is extracted directly from the ABAQUS output files. Thus, the cross-sectional stress is determined by

$$\sigma = F_X / A_0 \quad (2)$$

where A_0 is the initial cross-sectional area of honeycomb specimen.

The local stress history curves at some Lagrangian cross-sectional locations of honeycomb specimen under the two loading scenarios with $V = V_0 = 200$ m/s are shown in Fig. 3. For the two loading scenarios, the local stresses at a specific position have some similar features and a very distinctly different feature. The local stresses first keep at a relatively stable stage and then increase sharply from the initial crush state to a densification state. After densification, the local stress under constant-velocity compression remains almost unchanged, but that under direct impact is unloaded from the densification state to zero due to the decrease in impact velocity.

One-dimensional approximation is usually appropriate for uni-axial loading of cellular materials. One-dimensional stress distribution curves in honeycomb specimens under the two loading scenarios are presented in Fig. 4. For the case of constant-velocity compression, the stress behind the shock front keeps at a high-stress level and the stress levels are very different for different impact velocities; the stress ahead of the shock front keeps at a low-stress level, which does not change for different impact velocities. Thus, the initial crush stress for this loading scenario is insensitive to the impact velocity and it is identical to the quasi-static initial crush stress, as concluded by Barnes et al. [4-6] and Sun et al. [7], who determined the initial crush stress from the support end. For the case of direct impact, the stress in the region ahead of the shock front varies linearly from the free end to the location of initial crush. The point at which the linear segment ends is defined as the dynamic initial crush stress in this loading scenario, which is distinctly larger than the quasi-static initial crush stress. This finding coincides with that of Zheng et al. [3] and Ding et al. [8]. Therefore, the initial crush stress may be very different in different loading scenarios.

Figure 3: Local stress history under constant-velocity compression (left) and direct impact (right).

Figure 4: Local stress distribution under constant-velocity compression (left) and direct impact (right).

3.2 Local strain and strain rate

The local strain field calculation method based on the optimal local deformation gradient technique using the least square method [2] is employed to calculate the one-dimensional strain distribution in the loading direction of specimen. The optimal deformation gradient at a corner node i is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \mathbf{W}_i \cdot \mathbf{V}_i^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{V}_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{U}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{U}_{ij}^T, \quad \mathbf{W}_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{u}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{U}_{ij}^T \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of neighboring nodes of node i within a cut-off radius, superscript T denotes the transpose of a matrix, and \mathbf{U}_{ij} and \mathbf{u}_{ij} are the relative position vectors of nodes i and j in the reference and current configurations, respectively. The Lagrangian strain tensor, \mathbf{E} , is written as

$$\mathbf{E} = (\mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I}) / 2 \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. The local engineering strain in the loading direction is calculated by

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \sqrt{1 + 2E_{11}} \quad (5)$$

where E_{11} is the diagonal term of \mathbf{E} in the X direction. Through the error analysis [12], the optimal cut-off radius was found to be about 1.5 times of the average cell radius based on the reference configuration and 0.5 times of the average cell radius based on the current configuration.

The local strain history curves at some Lagrangian cross-sectional locations of honeycomb specimen under the two loading scenarios with $V = V_0 = 200$ m/s are shown in Fig. 5. Similar features can be observed, i.e. the local strain at any specific cross-sectional position changes sharply from the initial crush strain to the densification strain and keeps at the level of densification. The local strain distribution at any specific time can be determined by averaging the local engineering strain along the Y direction. The strain rate can be determined from the strain at a small interval of time. The local strain rate distribution curves at some specific time are presented in Fig. 6. Corresponding to the locations that the initial crush states are reached, the strain rates at initial crush can be determined, as illustrated in Fig. 6. It is indicated that for the case of constant-velocity compression, no matter how large the impact velocity is, the support end is at a low constant strain rate; for the case of direct impact, the strain rate at initial crush is relatively larger.

3.3 Strain rate effect on the initial crush stress

From Figs. 4 and 6, it is recognized that for the case of direct impact, the initial crush stress decrease with the decrease of strain rate, which is about $10^3 \sim 10^4$ /s. But, for the case of constant-velocity compression, the strain rate at initial crush is relatively small ($\sim 10^2$ /s). Therefore, the initial crush stress under constant-velocity compression has no strain-rate effect.

For the case of direct impact, the initial crush stress is larger than the quasi-static one because the strain rate is high and the strain-rate effect on the initial crush stress is obvious. A power-law fitting relation is introduced to characterize the strain-rate effect of strain rate on the initial crush stress, as

done by Ding et al. [8]. The relation between the initial crush stress σ_0^d and the local strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ can be expressed as

$$\sigma_0^d = \begin{cases} \sigma_0^{qs}, & \dot{\epsilon} \leq \dot{\epsilon}_{cr} \\ \sigma_0^{qs} (\dot{\epsilon} / \dot{\epsilon}_{cr})^n, & \dot{\epsilon} > \dot{\epsilon}_{cr} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where σ_0^{qs} is the quasi-static initial crush stress, $\dot{\epsilon}_{cr}$ a critical strain rate and n a fitting parameter. In this study, the parameters are fitted as $\sigma_0^{qs} = 0.75$ MPa, $\dot{\epsilon}_{cr} = 830$ /s and $n = 0.307$. The finding in this study solves the controversial issue of the strain rate effect on the initial crush stress in the literature [3-8]. For the case of high-constant-velocity compression, the region in the front of plastic compaction wave deforms in a quasi-static mode in which random shear bands exist. The local velocity is low and the local stress is evenly distributed, which leads to the low local strain rate in this region. For the case of direct impact, the region in the front of plastic compaction deforms in a shock mode in which the deformation is basically concentrated in a cell size near the shock front. The local velocity is high and the initial crush stress is raised by the local high strain rate.

Figure 5: Local strain history under constant-velocity compression (left) and direct impact (right).

Figure 6: Strain rate distribution under constant-velocity compression (left) and direct impact (right).

Figure 7: Variations of initial crush stress of irregular honeycombs with strain rate.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The seemingly contradictory understandings on the initial crush stress of cellular materials under dynamic loadings exist in the literature [3-8] and a comprehensive analysis of this issue is carried out with using direct information of local stress and strain from cell-based finite element models of irregular honeycombs under dynamic loadings in this study. The cross-sectional engineering stress calculation method [11] is employed to obtain the one-dimensional stress distribution in the loading direction by calculating the cross-sectional internal forces at different Lagrangian cross-sectional locations. The strain field calculation method [2, 12] based on the optimal local deformation gradient technique using the least square method is introduced to calculate the one-dimensional strain distribution in the loading direction of specimen. It is found that the stress ahead of the shock front obtained from the high-constant-velocity compression scenario is smaller than the quasi-static initial crush stress, but that obtained from the high-initial-velocity impact scenario is larger than the quasi-static initial crush stress. These understandings solve the divergence in the literature. The different conclusions on the initial crush stresses in the literature [3-8] are caused by using different loading scenarios, which lead to the different strain rates ahead of the shock front. The strain rate ($\sim 10^4/s$) ahead of the shock front of cellular material under high-initial-velocity impact is far larger than that under high-constant-velocity compression ($\sim 100/s$). When the local strain rate is not high, the initial crush stress remains as the quasi-static one. When the local strain is high enough, the initial crush stress increases with strain rate in a power-law fashion. Although different types of cellular materials have been used in the previous work, including irregular honeycomb [2], closed-cell foam [3, 8, 9], open-cell foam [4-6] and 2D virtual foam [7], we figure out that in different loading scenarios different deformation mechanisms lead to different strain rates and initial crush stresses.

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